

D9.3: Quality Management Plan

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1. Introduction

The overall objective of the project Quality Management Plan (QMP) is to have high quality in all aspects of the project implementation. The project draws inspiration from the PM2 project methodology on quality management that comprises the activities related to the identification, planning, execution, monitoring, and control of project quality-related activities.

To specify the methodology, standards, tools, and techniques used to support quality management, this project will follow the PM2 quality management process which comprises the activities related to the identification, planning, execution, and monitoring & control of project quality-related activities.

The main project quality objectives are:

- Define, and agree on the project's quality characteristics to be achieved throughout the project.
- Ensure quality assurance activities are performed as planned.
- Any non-conformity (or opportunity for quality improvements) is identified and implemented.
- Deliverables are accepted by the relevant stakeholders based on the defined quality/acceptance criteria.

2. Quality assurance of Research and Data management processes

A quality assurance procedure for data collection and data management will be established through transparent engagements and exploration with the respective WP leaders at project meetings. The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles will be adhered to throughout the research output management, open access to research outputs, and data management processes. The WP leaders that are not directly involved in the preparation of the deliverables will volunteer to review the quality of the deliverables based on their respective expertise. Advice and guidance will be sought from Executive Board (EB) or/and the Ethics Advisor or the External Advisory Board (EAB).

2.1 Data Quality Assurance

The data collection procedure will be established in collaboration with the WP leaders responsible for the tasks and subject to review within the WPs and approval by the Project Coordinators (PC). The procedure will specify how the relevant research and ethical considerations will be employed in the data collection processes, including the recruitment of participants, research methods and analysis, results, data storage, and dissemination to open science repositories, project websites, stakeholder groups, and the public.

2.2 Research Ethics

The data collection procedure will include a comprehensive Information Sheet that specifies the data selection and evaluation criteria, demography, the scope and purposes of the research, and participants' involvement. The procedures for creating the Informed Consent Form will be strictly adhered to, using inclusive, and concise language and clear terminologies. The duly signed Informed Consent Forms will be stored following national regulations or research ethics approval (if required).

2.3 Dataset

The quality of the datasets generated from the project will be assured through review by an expert not involved in data collection or members of the EAB. The WP leaders will ensure that recommendations or problems identified by the internal reviewer are solved before sending them to the PC.

The data (qualitative data) will be collected from workshops and interactive stakeholder events and will be fully anonymized and uploaded to appropriate open-access repositories and specific sections of the project's website. To ensure the inclusiveness and accessibility of the anonymized data, the WP leaders responsible for the tasks will translate the main finding into actionable guidelines and recommendations (e.g., search engines and algorithms) that will evolve from XR ethical usage into XR ethics standards.

3. Quality assurance for deliverables

The following deliverables which are described in the Grant Agreement will be subject to a quality assurance process throughout the project duration (see 3.1).

	Description	WP	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Status	Month
D1.1	Stakeholder engagement methodology and plan	WP1	XR4Europe	R	PU	3
D1.2	First report on stakeholder engagement activities and key metrics	WP1	XR4Europe	R	PU	18
D1.3	Second report on stakeholder engagement activities and key metrics	WP1	XR4Europe	R	PU	36
D1.4	Sustainability plan on legacy	WP1	XR4Europe	R	PU	36
D2.1	White paper/publication on state-of-the art in ethical frameworks, code of conduct, and good practices	WP2	UiO	R	PU	6
D2.2	White paper/publication on overview of possible forms of harm arising from XR risks	WP2	UiO	R	PU	24
D2.3	White paper/publication on model of harm that could arise from the use of XR technologies	WP2	UiO	R	PU	24
D2.4	White paper/publication on ethical issues beyond risks and harm	WP2	UiO	R	PU	24
D3.1	State-of-art in XR policy debates	WP3	KIT	R	PU	6
D3.2	XR regulatory gap analysis	WP3	KIT	R	PU	24
D3.3	Interoperability, ethical framework, and user rating policy roadmap	WP3	KIT	R	PU	36

D4.1	Report on existing and emerging standards and industry needs	WP4	OARC EU	R	PU	12
D4.2	XR Interoperability Guideline Document	WP4	OARC EU	R	PU	24
D5.1	Article on mapping of challenges and presentation of ethical, legal, regulatory, and technical interoperability solutions	WP5	USN	R	PU	21
D5.2	The Code of Conduct	WP5	USN	R	PU	36
D5.3	Protocols for the periodic update of the Code of Conduct	WP5	USN	R	PU	36
D6.1	Report on identifying and selection of use cases on good practices	WP6	Fraunhofer	R	PU	6
D6.2	Guidance on maintenance and development of the online platform	WP6	Fraunhofer	R	PU	24
D6.3	Report on evaluation results	WP6	Fraunhofer	R	PU	36
D7.1	XR literature and technology review report	WP7	IFE	R	PU	6
D7.2	XR stakeholders' needs, requirements, experience prioritized and integrated into the online knowledge management system	WP7	IFE	R	PU	18
D7.3	Educational materials specified and delivered online	WP7	IFE	R	PU	18
D7.4	Online rating repository	WP7	IFE	DEM	PU	24
D8.1	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication activities	WP8	NTUA	R	PU	3
D8.2	XR4Human branding: logo, aesthetics, website, and social media presence	WP8	NTUA	DEM	PU	4
D8.3	Release of the Promotional videos	WP8	NTUA	DEM	PU	12
D8.4	Release of the Promotional videos	WP8	NTUA	DEM	PU	24
D8.5	Release of the Promotional videos	WP8	NTUA	DEM	PU	34
D9.1	Data Management Plan	WP9	USN	DMP	PU	6
D9.2	Risk Management Plan	WP9	USN	OTHER	PU	6
D9.3	Quality Management Plan	WP9	USN	R	PU	6
D9.4	Knowledge Management Plan	WP9	USN	R	PU	6
D9.5	Innovation Management Plan	WP9	USN	R	PU	6

3.1 Quality assurance process for deliverables

All the deliverables must be reviewed by experts selected from members of the consortium or external reviewers if required. D9.1-5 deliverables will also be quality assured internally at USN, the coordinating institution.

The Reviewers will provide suggestions for improving the deliverables. The Author (s) and WP leader are required to implement the Reviewer's recommendations and send the first version and the revised (second) version to the PC for final approval and submission to the European Commission (EC).

The timelines for the quality assurance process include:

- One month before the submission deadline: The Author (s) provides the first draft of the deliverable to the Reviewer (s) who have volunteered in advance based on their expertise.
- Two weeks before the submission deadline: The reviewed deliverable is submitted to the PC for final review and approval.
- One week before the submission deadline: Final quality and formatting check and uploading to the portal by the PC.

3.2 Quality assurance process for dissemination

- The same quality assurance process for deliverables (see 3.1) will be applied during the dissemination of findings in high-impact peer-reviewed Open Science scientific journals, policy briefs, conferences and workshops presentations, and project milestones (via the XR4Human website and social media channels).

4. Quality of Records

4.1 Project Records

The PC, with the support of PMO, is responsible for maintaining the central records of projects including:

- Contractual documents
- Financial reports
- Correspondence with the EC
- Deliverables submitted to the EC.
- Correspondence with project partners
- Meeting minutes and progress reports (internal and external), and other important documents.
- All the official project documents and the latest deliverables are stored in the Participant Portal.

4.2 Quality assurance of Records and Archives

Microsoft Teams with accessibility by invite only is the chosen internal communication platform for XR4Human. Documents with the project participants as the target audience will be stored herein. Each partner will maintain records of all documents concerning them in their respective organizational storage systems, including:

- Documents (digital and/or paper form) stored are protected against damage, deterioration, or loss.
- Electronic records (digital files) and regular back-ups should be conducted.
- Storage of the first and latest versions of deliverables and project documents should be archived in their organization archive and linked to the project.

4.3 Naming System

The guidelines for naming files and documents (electronic form) will include labelling the files with the deliverable number and official name in the GA.

The file name(s) should have the version number (such as v0.1, v0.2, etc.) before the official release by the PC to the European Commission. For example:

- **D9.1_ Data Management Plan_v0.1.docx_** (Deliverable 9:1, Data Management Plan, draft version of the document released for collecting feedback within the consortium)
- **D9.1_ Data Management Plan_v0.1.docx_** (Deliverable 9.1, Data Management Plan, 1st version of the document released by PC)
- **D9.1_ Data Management Plan_v0.2.docx_** (2nd version of the deliverable released by PC)

5. Quality of Implementation and Risk Management

5.1 Work planning, monitoring, and control

- The PC will track and monitor the implementation of WPs tasks, expected outcomes, and impacts as specified in the project work plan. Any changes (significant changes or changes that will not affect the overall project) must be in line with contractual obligations and the rules of the EC and must be approved by the PC.
- The PC will set up joint calendar reminders along with email reminders to the WP leaders to ensure deadlines are reached (See 3.1 for deadline timeless). In cases of delays, the PC will inform the EC before the deadline, justify the delay, and suggest a new deadline.

5.2 Risk mitigation measures

- The Risk Management Plan is outlined in deliverable D9.1 Data Management Plan. The PM2 Risk Assessment Thresholds Matrix will be used to measure the risks identified in the project proposal phase.
- The PC will track and monitor these risks and initiate risk-mitigating measures throughout the project. The PC will report the identified risks to the EB, and the GA if the resolution of conflict is not reached.
- Each WP leader is responsible for identifying and reporting additional risks that may arise during the project implementation. The WP leader (s) will submit a risk report to the PC when the new risks are identified or with the progress report.

5.3 Project meetings

- A monthly WP leadership meeting will be conducted throughout the project (36 months)
- The coordinating institution is responsible for preparing all meeting minutes for all project meetings.
- Draft minutes will be shared with partners to add input within 5 working days (as agreed by partners). The final version will be stored in the project MS Teams channel.

5.4 Progress monitoring (internal reports)

- All partners will frequently prepare periodic reports of respective work progress reports (activities and target group progress) and financial reports of activities and send them to PC.
- The PC and the PMO will check all partner's progress reports as stipulated on the work plan and provide relevant feedback, advice, or guidance (HEU financial webinars) to check-mate deviations or below per performances.
- The EB meetings will be held monthly (online), and the GA meeting (physical) will be held once per year to update all partners on the project progress status.

5.5 Reports to the European Commission (external reports)

- The PC will ensure the timely submission of high-quality project reports with support from the PMO.
- The PC will further report and discuss project developments with the EB and GA, and the EAB will monitor the scientific quality of deliverables and report to the EC.

5.6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- To maximize the quality of impact of XR4Human activities (See 5.1) the following KPIs must be reached by the responsible partner to consider communication and dissemination activities as successful:

Channel	Tool	Indicator	M12	M24	M36
Website	Newsfeed	Number	15	30	60
	e-newsletters	Number	2	4	6
	visits	visits	250	100	2500
Social media	Twitter	followers/tweets re-tweets/likes	100/10 100/50	300/20 300/200	1000/500 500/500
	LinkedIn	Followers/posts	40/20	100/40	200/80
Scientific conferences	Oral/posters presentations	participations	4	8	12
Workshops	Participation	participations	5	10	15
Press release	Newspaper	Articles	1	2	4
	E-magazines	Articles	1	2	4
Electronic downloadable documents	Brochures or leaflets	Downloads	200	500	1000
Public events	Researcher's night	XR4HUMAN Booth	-	1	2
	Science communication events	Oral presentations	1	2	4
Scientific publications	Peer-reviewed articles/Opinion papers	Number of publications	-	2	4